

Study Techniques and Teacher Availability as Predictors of Academic Productivity of Stem Students in Private Schools in Davao City

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Abstract

Academic productivity is a key indicator of student success, particularly in demanding academic tracks such as the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand. This study examined the relationship and predictive influence of study techniques and teacher availability on the academic productivity of STEM students in private schools in Davao City, Philippines. Anchored on Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory, the study employed a quantitative predictive research design involving 150 senior high school STEM students selected through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a structured survey questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson's r correlation, and multiple linear regression. Results revealed that study techniques ($M = 3.72$), teacher availability ($M = 3.72$), and academic productivity ($M = 3.83$) were all rated high among respondents. Correlation analysis indicated a very strong positive relationship between study techniques and academic productivity ($r = 0.835$, $p < 0.001$) and between teacher availability and academic productivity ($r = 0.880$, $p < 0.001$). Regression analysis showed that study techniques explained 71.10% of the variance in academic productivity, while teacher availability explained 84.80%. When combined, the predictors accounted for 85.70% of the variance ($R^2 = 0.857$, $p < 0.001$). The findings highlight the importance of effective study strategies and responsive teacher support in enhancing STEM students' academic productivity.

Keywords: *study techniques, teacher availability, academic productivity, STEM education, self-efficacy.*

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Introduction

Academic productivity remains a critical indicator of student success, especially in highly demanding academic programs such as the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand. It refers to the learner's ability to perform well in academic tasks through effective learning strategies, motivation, and the application of higher-order thinking skills. According to Kyllonen et al. (2014), motivation is a key driver of student achievement, and when paired with strong study habits, it can significantly enhance a student's academic performance. However, without consistent development and practice of effective study techniques, academic performance is likely to suffer. Moreover, the role of teacher support is equally important; teachers' responsiveness, feedback, and accessibility serve as external motivators that enable students to perform at their full potential (Handa, 2020; Sabir et al., 2021).

Globally, the relationship between teacher involvement and student performance has been established in multiple contexts. For example, Ayllón et al. (2019), using over 86,000 student evaluations, demonstrated that teacher participation and support significantly enhance student self-efficacy and academic success. In Nigeria, Abe and Adu (2013) emphasized that teacher availability is one of the most influential factors in improving student performance, asserting that qualified and experienced teachers are essential for academic growth. Similarly, Gan et al. (2021) found that teacher feedback had a significant indirect effect on exam performance by shaping student motivation and feedback-seeking behavior. On the other hand, study techniques such as note-taking, reading comprehension, and collaborative learning have also been globally recognized as vital to academic success (Bui et al., 2013; Kandhro, 2015; Young et al., 2014).

In the Philippine context, researchers have similarly emphasized the role of both study techniques and teacher availability in supporting student achievement. Magulod Jr. (2018) found that Filipino university students in applied sciences exhibited moderate proficiency in time management, focus, and reading comprehension, all of which correlated with academic performance. Dungan et al. (2015) reported that study habits related to time management and learning environment significantly influenced student achievement. Locally, Arieta et al. (2017) highlighted that the study habits of senior high school students at Davao Doctors College were closely linked to their academic outcomes. Teacher availability, including qualities such as approachability and virtual responsiveness, has also been emphasized as a critical factor, particularly in the context of online or hybrid learning environments (Cinches et al., 2017; Satar & Akcan, 2018).

Despite existing literature, there is a noticeable gap in studies that integrate both study techniques and teacher availability as combined predictors of academic productivity—especially within the specialized context of STEM education in private schools in Davao City. Most existing studies have explored these variables independently or focused on general student populations. This gap presents an urgent need to understand how these two variables interact to influence student outcomes in a local, context-specific manner. Addressing this need, the present study investigates the significant relationship and influence of study techniques and teacher availability on the academic productivity of STEM students in selected private schools in Davao City.

Its findings aim to provide evidence-based recommendations that may inform instructional practices and academic support systems to boost student performance in high-demand academic environments.

This study aimed to assess the relationship and influence of study techniques and teacher availability on the academic productivity of STEM students in private schools in Davao City. Specifically, it sought to:

1. Determine the level of study techniques (reading method, note-taking, group study), teacher availability (virtual responses, feedback quality, approachability), and academic productivity (motivation, effective study habits, critical thinking skills).
2. Investigate the significant relationship between study techniques and academic productivity; Teacher Availability and Academic Productivity.
3. Investigate the significant combined influence of study techniques and teacher availability on academic productivity.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between study techniques and academic productivity, Teacher Availability and Academic Productivity.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of study techniques and teacher availability on academic productivity.

Theoretical / Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on Bandura’s Self-Efficacy Theory, which posits that belief in one’s capability to perform tasks significantly influences outcomes. The theory’s core constructs—mastery experiences, vicarious experiences, verbal persuasion, and emotional states—correspond with academic processes. Effective study techniques foster mastery, while teacher support offers encouragement, guidance, and modeling.

Conceptually, the study is framed around the interaction of two independent variables (study techniques and teacher availability) with one dependent variable (academic productivity), emphasizing their roles in student motivation, habits, and critical thinking.

The conceptual framework for this study is illustrated below:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Conceptual Framework Showing Academic Relationship

Method

This study employs a quantitative predictive research design. It was used to investigate the relationships between study techniques, teacher availability, and academic productivity without manipulating the variables.

The study was conducted at private senior high schools in Davao City offering STEM strands. These institutions are known for their academic rigor and structured programs aimed at developing science-oriented competencies.

The respondents consisted of 150 senior high school students under the STEM strand. Stratified random sampling was employed to ensure representative coverage across grade levels and sections. This technique allowed each subgroup within the population to be proportionally represented. This method ensured that the perspectives gathered reflected the diversity of students in terms of academic experience and exposure to teacher support. Such a sampling approach also minimized selection bias and improved the reliability of the results.

The data gathering process began by securing approval from the Research Ethics Committee, followed by obtaining consent from school principals and the participating students. Once approved, the researcher disseminated the questionnaire through Google Forms, ensuring accessibility and safety. The responses were monitored in real-time and collected over a specified period. After collection, the data were tabulated and submitted for statistical analysis.

Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to evaluate the levels of study techniques, teacher availability, and academic productivity. Pearson's r was used to determine the significance and strength of the relationships between variables. Multiple linear regression identified specific domains that significantly influenced academic productivity.

The study ensured ethical compliance by obtaining informed consent, maintaining confidentiality, and explaining the study's purpose to participants. Data collection was conducted online to reduce health risks. The principles of transparency, voluntary participation, and fairness were strictly observed.

Results

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics of the three core variables, Study Techniques, Teacher Availability, and Academic Productivity, along with their indicators. All components were rated “High” in terms of frequency or agreement, indicating that these behaviors and experiences are frequently practiced or observed among STEM students in selected private schools in Davao City.

Table 1. Descriptive Table

Variables and Their Indicators	Standard Deviation	Mean	Verbal Description
Study Techniques	1.086	3.72	High
Reading Method	1.049	3.70	High
Note-taking Method	1.090	3.66	High
Group Study Method	1.115	3.79	High
Teacher Availability	1.055	3.72	High
Virtual Responses	1.029	3.55	High

Feedback Quality	1.001	3.81	High
Approachability	1.115	3.80	High
Academic Productivity	1.075	3.83	High
Motivation	1.093	3.90	High
Effective Study Habits	1.102	3.89	High
Critical Thinking	1.021	3.71	High

Among study techniques, Group Study Method had the highest mean ($M = 3.79$), reinforcing the claim that collaborative learning is highly effective for many students. However, it is important to note that group study effectiveness may depend on individual learning styles and student dynamics. Note-taking Method ($M = 3.66$), although slightly lower, remains essential for learning.

Meanwhile, under Teacher Availability, Feedback Quality ($M = 3.81$) and Approachability ($M = 3.80$) were rated the highest. Virtual Responses ($M = 3.55$), while still rated high, may reflect gaps in digital communication and consistency.

Moreover, for Academic Productivity, the highest indicators were Motivation ($M = 3.90$) and Effective Study Habits ($M = 3.89$), indicating that students are generally driven and apply strategic learning methods. Critical Thinking ($M = 3.71$), though slightly lower, still indicates a strong capacity among students to analyze and evaluate information effectively.

Overall, the high ratings across all variables suggest that STEM students in Davao's private schools possess strong learning strategies and are supported by teachers who provide meaningful feedback and are approachable. These findings align with broader educational research and reinforce the value of strengthening both internal and external academic support systems.

Table 2. Test of Relationships

Independent Variables	Academic Productivity			
	r-value	p-value	Decision on H_0	Interpretation
Study Techniques	0.835	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant
Teacher Availability	0.880	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant

The correlation results indicate a very high positive relationship between study techniques and academic productivity, with an r-value of 0.835 and a p-value of 0.000, which is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This suggests that the more frequently students employ effective study strategies such as reading, note-taking, and group study methods, the higher their levels of academic productivity tend to be. Similarly, teacher availability also demonstrated a very high positive correlation with academic productivity, as evidenced by an r-value of 0.880 and a p-value of 0.000. This implies that students who experience greater access to their teachers through virtual responsiveness, clear feedback, and general approachability tend to be more motivated, disciplined, and cognitively engaged in their studies.

Table 3. Test of Influence

Predictors	Academic Productivity				
	R ² -value	F-value	p-value	Decision on H_0	Interpretation
Study Techniques	71.10%	363.228	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant

Teacher Availability	84.80%	823.028	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Combined Influence	85.70%	441.295	0.000	Reject H₀	Significant

Table 3 illustrates that both Study Techniques and Teacher Availability significantly influence Academic Productivity among STEM students in private schools in Davao City. Specifically, Study Techniques account for 71.10% of the variance in academic productivity ($F = 363.228, p = 0.000$), while Teacher Availability explains an even greater proportion at 84.80% ($F = 823.028, p = 0.000$). When considered together, their combined influence reaches 85.70% ($F = 441.295, p = 0.000$), confirming that both internal and external academic factors play a vital role in students' performance. In this context, effective study techniques such as time management, note-taking, and self-regulated learning foster a sense of control and competence, while the availability and support of teachers provide necessary feedback, guidance, and reassurance, further reinforcing students' self-efficacy. As students gain confidence in their academic abilities through both personal effort and institutional support, they are more likely to engage actively in learning tasks, persist through challenges, and achieve higher levels of productivity.

Discussion

The results of this study provide compelling evidence that both study techniques and teacher availability play critical roles in the academic productivity of STEM students in private schools in Davao City. All variables measured study techniques, teacher availability, and academic productivity received High descriptive ratings. This suggests that students are consistently engaging in effective academic strategies and receiving substantial support from their teachers, both of which contribute positively to their learning outcomes.

The descriptive findings show that STEM students in private schools in Davao City exhibited high levels in study techniques ($M = 3.72$), teacher availability ($M = 3.72$), and academic productivity ($M = 3.83$). Among study techniques, group study ($M = 3.79$) was most used, reflecting the benefits of peer collaboration in building confidence and understanding (Kandhro, 2015; Gebremariam et al., 2023). Note-taking ($M = 3.66$) and reading ($M = 3.70$) also rated high, supporting findings that these methods aid retention and critical thinking (Bui et al., 2013; Balan et al., 2019).

For teacher availability, feedback quality ($M = 3.81$) and approachability ($M = 3.80$) were strongest, emphasizing the role of supportive teachers in boosting motivation (Handa, 2020; Gan et al., 2021). Virtual responses ($M = 3.55$) were slightly lower, suggesting room for improvement in digital communication (Dereshiwsky, 2013). In academic productivity, motivation ($M = 3.90$) and effective study habits ($M = 3.89$) led, showing students' strong drive and discipline (Kyllonen et al., 2014; Abdulrahman et al., 2021). Critical thinking ($M = 3.71$) also showed solid engagement (Walker & Kettler, 2020).

Study techniques, composed of reading methods, note-taking, and group study, were found to have a significant positive correlation with academic productivity ($r = 0.835, p = .000$). This finding aligns with previous studies emphasizing the importance of personalized and structured study behaviors (Bhat, 2022; Arieta et al., 2017; Grohol, 2020). Reading as a technique enhances comprehension and critical thinking (Balan et al., 2019), while note-taking reinforces retention and focus (Bui et al., 2013). Group

study further builds social learning and deepens conceptual understanding through peer exchange (Kandhro, 2015).

Similarly, teacher availability measured through virtual responsiveness, feedback quality, and approachability showed a very high positive correlation with academic productivity ($r = 0.880$, $p = .000$). These findings are supported by research indicating that students are more likely to succeed when they receive timely, constructive feedback and feel comfortable seeking help from their teachers (Fehintola, 2014; Gan et al., 2021; Handa, 2020). The accessibility of teachers, especially in blended or online learning environments, significantly influences students' motivation, confidence, and persistence (Dereshiwsky, 2013; Sabir, 2021).

A multiple regression analysis confirmed the combined effect of these two factors. The model that included both study techniques and teacher availability accounted for 85.7% of the variance in academic productivity ($R^2 = 0.857$), compared to 84.8% when teacher availability alone was considered. These findings mirror those of earlier studies (Magulod, 2018; Amaro-Jimenez et al., 2020), confirm the relevance of Piaget's Cognitive Learning Theory, which emphasizes the active integration of knowledge through effective learning strategies. The interaction between independent learning habits and instructional guidance highlights the importance of a balanced educational approach in the STEM curriculum.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it is concluded that both study techniques and teacher availability significantly and positively influence the academic productivity of STEM students in private schools in Davao City. Among these variables, teacher availability stands out as the stronger individual predictor, but study techniques also contribute meaningfully to academic outcomes. These findings validate theoretical frameworks that emphasize self-efficacy and cognitive engagement, and they underscore the importance of a supportive learning environment paired with active student participation in their learning process. The study affirmed Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory, where both mastery experiences (e.g., study strategies) and external support (e.g., teacher feedback and presence) reinforce a student's belief in their capability to succeed.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, it is recommended that a multifaceted approach be adopted to enhance the academic productivity of STEM students. Educational policymakers, particularly the Department of Education, should prioritize the integration of structured study skills training and teacher development programs that emphasize responsiveness and effective feedback mechanisms. School administrators are encouraged to create systems and policies that foster consistent and meaningful teacher-student interactions, especially in digital and hybrid learning environments. Teachers may recognize the impact of their availability and feedback on student motivation and learning outcomes and, therefore, should maintain timely communication channels and adopt strategies that promote student engagement and understanding. Students, on their part, should be trained to adopt effective study techniques—especially those related to reading comprehension and collaborative learning—as these have been shown to significantly influence academic performance. Parents can also contribute by fostering a home environment conducive to disciplined study habits and minimizing distractions. Finally, future researchers are encouraged to undertake qualitative investigations or longitudinal studies to further explore the

dynamics between instructional support and student learning processes, thereby providing deeper insights and practical frameworks for implementation.

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